

From Data to Credits: Using ReadMe, Markdown, and Dublin Core for Better Documentation.

The basics of the “ReadMe”:

- provide a meta-data description of your project, so that you and other have a glimpse of idea what's inside your folder/files/repository – any information is better than nothing
- root folder should have generic ReadMe followed by descriptive ReadMe in each subfolder
- in the simplest way provide ASCII text file describing your work avoiding .docx or .odt
- it is usually a simple plain-text file called READ.ME, README.TXT, ReadMe.md Or README
- often simple ReadMe.md formatted in the human readable Markdown markup language^[1]
- some guidance can be found in Ref.^[2] and a list of best practice READMEs in Ref.^[3]

The contents of the “ReadMe”:

- rule of thumb: document relevant details about data collection, processing, and analysis
- minimum information: title, creator, contact, file naming convention, folder structure, description of data (5W1H+R^[4]: What? When? Where? Who? Why? How? +Relationship), license, and ...as much information as possible

Where to go from here: For interoperability of metadata use the Dublin Core standard^[5] with XML-schema or JSON-LD^[6].

References:

[1] <https://daringfireball.net/projects/markdown/syntax>

[2] <https://www.makeareadme.com/>

[3] <https://github.com/matiassingers/awesome-readme>

[4] Subramaniam, Pranav / Ma, Yintong / Li, Chi / Mohanty, Ipsita / Fernandez, Raul Castro Comprehensive and Comprehensible Data Catalogs: The What, Who, Where, When, Why, and How of Metadata Management 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.07532>

[5] https://dublincore.org/resources/userguide/creating_metadata/

[6] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON-LD>

README.md

```
# Title
Paper/Project/Thesis/Dataset
(The name given to the paper/project/thesis/dataset.)

# Creator
Jay Doe
(Who created the resource and is primarily responsible? Can be a repetitive list of authors, artists,
collectors, organizations etc.)

# Creator.ORCID
0000-0001-2345-6789
(ORCID identifier of the Creator)

# Creator.Email
jaydoe@domain.edu
(email identifier of the Creator)

# Publisher
Institute of Fancy Science
Department of Amazing Science
Imaginary Street 42
D-01234 ImaginaryTown
Country
(The department/institute responsible for making the resource available.)

# Description
Exemplary test case to verify the simulation tools and compare to the experiment.
Data have been published at Zenodo under CC-BY 4.0, see https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.XYZ .
(A textual description of the content of the resource.)

# Subject
* Experimental Data
* Abbreviation: NMR, SAXS
* (Phrase\Keywords describing the content of the resource.)

# Date
2025-02-14
(A date associated with the creation or availability of the resource. Recommended format: YYYY-MM-DD)

# Language
en-US; de-DE
(The language of the resource recommended as BCP 47 language tag.)

# Format
* csv
* pdf
* (The data format to identify the software and possibly hardware that
might be needed to display or operate the resource.
For a list of MIME types see [here](https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml)).

# Method
Method01XYZ hasURL https://github.com/FakeUser/FakeProject/releases/tag/v1.0
Method01XYZ hasDependency https://github.com/FakeProjectDependsOn/releases/tag/v2.2.2
Method01XYZ hasDOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.ZYX
(Refer to your (post-)processing tools/methods, e.g. URL or git hash)

# Type
Text
(The category of the resource e.g. Collection, Dataset, Event, Image, Experiment, Simulation, Report, Text,
Draft, Image. See also [DCMI Type Vocabulary](https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-
terms/#section-7/).)

# Coverage
2024-2025
(Temporal coverage is typically a period for acquiring the data.)

# Source
PhD-Thesis IsPartOf https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.ABC
(Information about a second resource from which the present resource is derived - if applicable.)

# Relation
Experiment IsPartOf PhD-Thesis
PhD-Thesis IsReferencedBy https://doi.org/10.5281/DOI.OF.PAPER
(An identifier to provide a relationship from source to the present resource,
e.g. IsVersionOf, IsReplacedBy, IsPartOf, IsReferencedBy, see [Qualified Dublin Core
Terms](https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/))

# Identifier
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.PUBLISHED_THESIS
(An unique identifier of the resource, e.g. DOI, ISBN, Number)

# Rights
CC-BY-4.0 hasURL https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
(A rights management statement of the resource, e.g. license for publishing and sharing.)
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- ✓ structured layout with minimal information including relational identifiers (similar to [rdf-schema](#))
 - ✓ simple parsing and machine processing is possible between '#' section to archive interoperability
 - ✓ minimal standard in analogy to Dublin Core identifiers